

Structural analysis and biochemical properties of laccase enzymes from two *Pediococcus* species

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1 SUMMARY

2 Prokaryotic laccases are emergent biocatalysts. However, they have not been broadly
3 found and characterized in bacterial organisms, especially in lactic acid bacteria.
4 Recently, a prokaryotic laccase from the lactic acid bacterium *Pediococcus acidilactici*
5 5930, which can degrade biogenic amines, was discovered. Thus, our study aimed to shed
6 light on laccases from lactic acid bacteria focusing on two *Pediococcus* laccases, *P.*
7 *acidilactici* 5930 and *Pediococcus pentosaceus* 4806, which have provided valuable
8 information on their biochemical activities on redox mediators and biogenic amines. Both
9 laccases are able to oxidize canonical substrates as ABTS, ferrocyanide and 2,6-DMP,
10 and non-conventional substrates as biogenic amines. With ABTS as a substrate, they
11 prefer an acidic environment and show sigmoidal kinetic activity, and are rather
12 thermostable. Moreover, this study has provided the first structural view of two lactic acid
13 bacteria laccases, revealing new structural features not seen before in other well-studied
14 laccases, but which seem characteristic for this group of bacteria. We believe that
15 understanding the role of laccases in lactic acid bacteria will have an impact on their
16 biotechnological applications and provide a framework for the development of
17 engineered lactic acid bacteria with enhanced properties.

18 INTRODUCTION

19
20 Laccases (benzenediol: oxygen oxidoreductases; EC 1.10.3.2) are common enzymes in
21 nature belonging to the multicopper oxidases (MCO) group (Sirim, *et al.* 2011). They
22 contain four copper atoms that differ in their spectroscopic and electro-paramagnetic
23 resonance (EPR) properties: a mononuclear Type 1 copper (T1Cu) that is responsible for
24 the blue color of these enzymes (blue laccases), with a strong electronic absorbance
25 around 610 nm and detectable by EPR (Guan, *et al.* 2018); a Type 2 copper (T2Cu), which
26 is colorless but detectable by EPR; and two Type 3 copper ions (T3Cu) showing a weak
27 absorbance near 300 nm and are not detectable by EPR. The T1Cu accepts an electron
28 from the substrate, while the T2Cu and the two T3Cu form a trinuclear cluster and transfer
29 electrons from the T1Cu to an O₂ molecule, which is reduced to H₂O (Chandra and
30 Chowdhary 2015, Su, *et al.* 2018). Laccases possess conserved amino acid motifs
31 responsible for binding to copper atoms that are composed mainly of His-Cys (T1Cu) and
32 His (trinuclear T2-T3 centers) residues (Su, *et al.* 2018). Laccases catalyze direct
33 oxidation of *ortho*- and *para*-diphenols, aminophenols, polyphenols, polyamines, and
34 aryl diamines, as well as a few inorganic ions. Some substrates cannot be oxidized directly
35 by laccases because of their high redox potential or a steric hindrance. They can, however,
36 be oxidized with the help of low molecular weight redox mediators (Kunamneni, *et al.*
37 2008). Redox mediators are diffusible electron carriers, which once oxidized by laccase,
38 can oxidize bulky or high-redox potential compounds which otherwise are not oxidized
39 by laccase alone (Mateljak, *et al.* 2019). Structurally laccases are either monomeric or
40 homodimeric proteins with an average molecular mass of 60-100-kDa (Madhavi and Lele
41 2009). They can be classified as two or three domain enzymes having the cupredoxin fold
42 as a common signature, which suggests that this protein is the common ancestor

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3 43 (Chauhan, *et al.* 2017). Laccase catalytic activity has been described in a wide range of
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5 44 biological functions such as spore resistance and pigmentation, lignification of plant cell
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8 45 walls, lignin biodegradation, humus turnover, detoxification processes, virulence factors
9
10 46 and iron homeostasis (Kunamneni, *et al.* 2007). Laccases have been isolated from a range
11
12 47 of animals, different plants, fungi, and bacteria (Chauhan, *et al.* 2012), although most
13
14 48 characterized laccases were obtained from fungi, especially white-rot fungi, known as
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16
17 49 efficient lignin degraders. Bioinformatics studies on laccases have indicated that they are
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19 50 present in various high G+C Gram-positive bacteria and α -, γ -, and ϵ -proteobacteria and
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21 51 archaea (Alexandre and Zhulin 2000, Sharma, *et al.* 2007, Ausec, *et al.* 2011). However,
22
23 52 their possible applications are not well explored; only a few prokaryotic laccase enzymes
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25
26 53 have been purified and analyzed (Sharma, *et al.* 2007, Reiss, *et al.* 2013, Fernandes, *et al.*
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28 54 2014), mainly from the genera *Bacillus* and *Streptomyces*, but also from other eubacteria
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30 55 and archeon species (Rosconi, *et al.* 2005, Sharma, *et al.* 2007, Galai, *et al.* 2009, Hsiao,
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32 56 *et al.* 2011, Reiss, *et al.* 2013, Ausec, *et al.* 2015, Martins, *et al.* 2015, Mathews, *et al.*
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34 57 2016, Afreen, *et al.* 2017, Basheer, *et al.* 2017, Rezaei, *et al.* 2017). Genes from unknown
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37 58 α - and γ -proteobacterium and metagenomes have been also cloned, expressed, purified,
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40 59 and characterized (Singh, *et al.* 2011). Recently, two multicopper oxidases (MCO) from
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42 60 lactic acid bacteria (LAB) *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* (basonym: *L. plantarum*) J16
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44 61 and *Pediococcus acidilactici* CECT 5930 obtained from wine and cereal, respectively
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47 62 (Callejón, *et al.* 2014), have been identified as genuine laccases (Callejón, *et al.* 2016,
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49 63 Callejón, *et al.* 2017). More recently the characterization of a MCO from a strain of LAB
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51 64 *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* (basonym: *Lactobacillus fermentum*) has been reported
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54 65 (Xu and Fang 2019). These three LAB enzymes have an interesting technological
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56 66 capacity, the degradation of biogenic amines (BA), which are toxic for humans (Ladero,
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58 67 *et al.* 2010, Russo, *et al.* 2010, Russo, *et al.* 2016).
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3 68 Differences between fungal and prokaryotic laccases include the cellular localization, the
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5 69 redox potential, optimal physicochemical reaction conditions, substrate range and the
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8 70 specific activity, and in some cases, tertiary structure. In biotechnological processes,
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10 71 mainly fungal laccases have been used (Machczynski, *et al.* 2004). However, bacterial
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12 72 laccases could overcome some limitations of fungal laccases. In this regard, prokaryotic
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14 73 laccases can catalyze reactions in a wider pH range, exhibit higher thermal stability, can
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16 74 be more easily expressed, can feasibly be improved by genetic engineering, and are more
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18 75 tolerant towards organic solvents, high salt concentrations, and common laccase
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20 76 inhibitors than fungal enzymes (Machczynski, *et al.* 2004, Gunne 2014, Callejón, *et al.*
21
22 77 2017). Although multiple applications have been described for bacterial laccases
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24 78 (Martins, *et al.* 2015, Chauhan, *et al.* 2017), very few have been commercialized to date.
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26 79 High-resolution three-dimensional structures for bacterial laccases have been solved,
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28 80 with CotA from *B. subtilis* and CueO from *E. coli* being the best known (Roberts, *et al.*
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30 81 2002, Enguita, *et al.* 2003, Hakulinen and Rouvinen 2015). However, no three-
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32 82 dimensional structure of any LAB laccase has previously been determined. Here, we
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34 83 biochemically characterize a new laccase from *Pediococcus pentosaceus* that shows
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36 84 similar catalytic properties to the laccase from the previously described *P. acidilactici*
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38 85 (Callejón, *et al.* 2017) but degrades tyramine to a higher extent. We describe the structures
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40 86 of both LAB laccases, which notably contain an extended Met-rich C-terminus, a feature
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42 87 not observed before in other laccases.
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51 89 RESULTS

52 90 **Sequence analysis, cloning and expression of the *P. pentosaceus* 4816 laccase**

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56 91 The gene PEPE_0502 codes for a putative MCO in the *P. pentosaceus* ATCC 25745
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58 92 genome (NCBI ABJ67595.1). Based on this sequence, the primers LacaPepe1 and
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93 LacaPepe2 were designed to clone the *P. pentosaceus* 4816 MCO gene, obtaining a
94 fragment of 1800 bp. Protein sequence analysis showed the four conserved copper ligand
95 motifs characteristic of the MCO family (Su, *et al.* 2018) (Fig. 1). This protein (Pp4816),
96 shows 59% sequence identity with the Pa5930 laccase previously described (Callejón, *et*
97 *al.* 2017).

98 The Pp4816 gene was cloned into the pET28a expression plasmid and the resulting
99 construct (pET28a-Pp4816) was transformed into *E. coli* BL21(DE3) pGro7. Cell-free
100 extracts of eleven transformed clones with or without induction by isopropyl- β -D-
101 thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) were analyzed for ABTS oxidation activity and by SDS-
102 PAGE. All of the induced extracts showed a strong ABTS oxidation activity and a protein
103 band absent in non-induced extracts.

104 Recombinant Pp4816 laccase containing a 6xHis-tag was purified from the crude extract
105 by metal-chelating chromatography on Ni²⁺-NTA agarose (Fig. 2A). After purification,
106 the amount of recombinant laccase protein from a 2 L cell culture was around 91 mg.

107 **Characterization of the recombinant Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases**

108 Electrophoretic mobility on SDS-polyacrylamide gel (Fig. 2A) revealed a Pp4816
109 apparent molecular weight of around 64 kD, including the poly-His-tag (2.5 kD).

110 The purified recombinant protein showed a deep blue color and exhibited a maximum
111 peak at 600 nm in the UV-visible absorption spectrum (Fig. 2B), which corresponds to
112 the characteristic T1 copper center absorbance peak of the MCOs (Guan, *et al.* 2018).

113 To determine kinetic parameters of recombinant Pp4816 laccase for substrate ABTS, the
114 increase in OD₄₂₀ over time for different substrate concentrations was recorded.
115 Surprisingly, the experimental curve of initial rates against ABTS concentration was

Preferred position of Figure 1

Preferred position of Figure 2

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3 116 slightly sigmoidal. By fitting these data to an empirical equation for sigmoidal enzyme
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5 117 kinetics, a k_{cat} and a $K_{0.5}$ of $10.1 \pm 2.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.31 \pm 0.03 \text{ mM}$, respectively, were
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7 118 determined (Table 1). Previously, we did not appreciate a sigmoid behaviour for the
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9 119 homologous laccase Pa5930 (Callejón, *et al.* 2017); however, after more detailed kinetic
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11 120 analysis, sigmoidal kinetics were also found. After the sigmoidal fitting for the Pa5930
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13 121 laccase, the values of $k_{cat} = 2.31 \pm 0.26 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $K_{0.5} = 0.33 \pm 0.04 \text{ mM}$ were obtained (Table
14
15 122 1). Curiously, with both enzymes, the sigmoidal kinetic profile was only observed with
16
17 123 ABTS and not with other substrates typical of laccases as ferrocyanide and 2,6-DMP (Fig.
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19 124 S1). The rate data of both enzymes with these two substrates were fitted to hyperbolic
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21 125 curves (Figure S1). The kinetic parameters for 2,6-DMP and ferrocyanide are shown in
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23 126 Table 1.

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29 127 On the substrate ABTS, Pp4816 was active only at acidic pH, with a maximum around
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31 128 pH 3.0-3.5, and was inactive above pH 4.5. For 2,6-DMP, the maximum activity was
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33 129 detected around pH 8.0-8.5 (Fig. 2C), whereas no activity was detected against guaiacol
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35 130 in the pH range and conditions used. The optimal temperature for ABTS oxidation was
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37 131 in the range 55-65°C, although the enzyme showed more than 50% activity in the range
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39 132 of 37 to 70°C (Fig. 2D). Thermal resistance experiments showed that Pp4816 laccase is
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41 133 a relatively thermostable enzyme, showing a T_{50} (defined as the temperature at which the
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43 134 enzyme retains 50% of its activity after a 5 min incubation) of 83.7°C (Fig. 2E). Its highest
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45 135 activity was found after 5 min treatment at 65°C; at this temperature the recorded activity
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47 136 was even higher than those found at lower temperatures. Heat treatments above 75°C
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49 137 dramatically decreased the laccase activity (Fig. 2E).

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55 138 ABTS was a remarkably efficient mediator for 2,6-DMP oxidation at pH 4.0, and
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57 139 mediated oxidation of some biogenic amines (see below). We also investigated the
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59 140 oxidation of 2,6-DMP by both recombinant laccases using two other well-known laccase

Preferred position of Table 1

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3 141 redox mediators, HBT and TEMPO, which act through distinct reaction mechanisms
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5 142 (Guan, et al. 2018). HBT and TEMPO failed, as these two compounds were not substrates
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7 143 of Pp4816 and Pa5916 laccases at pH 4.0 or pH 7.5 (results not shown).
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10 144 **Effect of putative inhibitor compounds on Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases**

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14 145 Different potential inhibitors were tested on both recombinant enzymes. The enzymatic
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16 146 activity in the presence of 1 mM inhibitor is shown in Fig. 3. The corresponding inhibitor
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18 147 equivalents (inhibitor/enzyme molar ratios) were 6800 for laccase Pp4816 and 6560 for
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20 148 enzyme Pa5930. Semicarbazide, sodium azide, and cysteine completely inhibited the
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23 149 ABTS-oxidizing activity of both enzymes. Bipyridil, thioglycolic acid, phenanthroline,
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25 150 and zinc chloride diminished their activity by 50% or more, whereas clorgyline,
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27 151 pargyline, NaCl, NaF and EDTA decreased the activity of Pa5930 laccase but exerted a
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29 152 lesser inhibitory effect on Pp4816 enzyme. Cyclopropylamine, deprenyl, and rasagiline
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31 153 decreased the activity of both laccases by less than 25%. In general, both enzymes showed
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33 154 similar behavior for the tested compounds, although Pa5930 laccase seemed to be more
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35 155 sensitive to inhibitors, with the exception of cyclopropylamine and rasagiline.
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40 156 **Biogenic amine-oxidizing activity of Pa5930 and Pp4816 laccases**

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43 157 The activities of both laccases were tested on the biogenic amines (BA) most frequently
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45 158 found in foods: tyramine, histamine, and putrescine. In addition, two structurally related
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47 159 amines have been included in the analysis: dopamine and phenylethylamine. Neither of
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49 160 the laccases was able to degrade histamine, putrescine, or phenylethylamine in the
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51 161 conditions tested, either with or without a mediator (ABTS). Both enzymes were able to
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53 162 oxidize tyramine, although only in the presence of mediator. After 24 hours of incubation
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55 163 with enzyme and mediator, 93% of the tyramine was oxidized by Pp4816, while 70% was
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57 164 oxidized by Pa5930. Dopamine was oxidized in the presence and absence of mediator
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3 165 (Table 2). Pa5930 is apparently more dependent on the ABTS mediator than Pp4816.
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5 166 After 24 hours of incubation with mediator, the degradation of dopamine was almost
6
7 167 complete for both enzymes. However, in the absence of the ABTS mediator, the
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9 168 degradation of dopamine with Pa5930 laccase decreased by approximately half, while it
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11 169 was nearly the same with the enzyme Pp4816.
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15 170 Structures of laccase Pa5930 and Pp4816.

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18 171 Crystals were obtained for both laccases which diffracted X-rays to 2.3 Å resolution for
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20 172 Pp4816 and to 2.5 Å or 2.0 Å for Pa5930 crystals grown in Tris-HCl pH 8.5 or HEPES
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22 173 pH 7.5, respectively (Table 3). The structure of Pa5930 (residues 1 to 477) at both pHs is
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24 174 similar, albeit the C-terminus which was not completely traced due to the absence of
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26 175 electron density, indicating that the last residues are disordered. The structure was traced
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28 176 till residue 461 at pH 8.5 and till residue 471 at pH 7.5 (Fig. S2). Overall, the structures
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30 177 of both *Pediococcus* laccases are highly similar (RMSD 0.9 Å for 456 residues) despite
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32 178 having an extended C-terminus for Pp4816 (Fig. 4A). Both laccases are monomeric and
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34 179 show three cupredoxin-like domains (Pfam CL0026), containing four copper ions bound
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36 180 (Fig. 4A). The overall fold and copper-binding sites are similar to laccases CueO from *E.*
37
38 181 *coli* and CotA from *B. subtilis* (Enguita, *et al.* 2003, Komori, *et al.* 2014) (RMSD values
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40 182 shown at Table S1) (Fig. S3). Close examination of domain 1 (residues 1-168 for Pa5930
41
42 183 and residues 1-170 for Pp4816) reveals that the first N-terminal 25 residues have an
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44 184 extended coil conformation that lies on the protein surface, partially at the interface
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46 185 between domain 2 and 3 (Fig. 4B). This feature was specific for Pa5930 and Pp4816, as
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48 186 it is was not observed in CotA and CueO (Fig. 4B). Subsequent secondary structural
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50 187 elements of domain 1 are similar to CueO, with nine strands forming a β-barrel and one
51
52 188 α-helix. Meanwhile, domain 2 (residues 174-313 for Pa5930 and 176-316 for Pp4816)
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54 189 contains 12 strands with a β-barrel form connected to domain 3 through a long coil region
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Preferred position of Table 2

Preferred position of Figure 4

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3 190 of 22 residues similarly to CueO and CotA. However, the *Pediococcus* laccases lack an
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5 191 extended loop connecting β 20- β 21 present in CueO and CotA (Fig. 4C). Domain 3 was
6
7 192 formed by ten strands with a β -barrel form and one short α -helix followed by an extended
8
9 193 C-terminus, a feature not present in CotA and CueO. This extension is 32-residues longer
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11 194 for Pp4816, which has two additional α -helices (Fig. 4C). *Pediococcus* laccases do not
12
13 195 contain the methionine-rich region observed in domain 3 of CueO (14 Met and 5 His in
14
15 196 45 residues) that is proposed to bind additional coppers (Singh, *et al.* 2011), but
16
17 197 surprisingly their C-terminus contains a high number of Met residues (Figs. 1 and S5).
18
19 198 The C-terminus of Pp4816 contains 9 Met, though no His, versus the rest of the protein
20
21 199 (11 Met in 461 residues) and similarly, Pa5930 contains 3 Met and 3 His at the C-terminus
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23 200 versus the rest of the protein (12 Met in 459 residues) (Figs. 1, 4D and S5A). Interestingly,
24
25 201 one α -helix at the C-terminus of Pp4816 structurally aligns with the CueO Met-rich
26
27 202 insertion (Figs. 4C and S5A) and five Met residues formed a hydrophobic patch at the
28
29 203 protein surface (Fig. S5B). Sequence alignment reveals this Met-rich region at the C-
30
31 204 terminus is common in LAB laccases, with some having even longer extensions than
32
33 205 Pp4816, and some with His-rich C-termini (Figs. 1 and S4).

206 **Copper coordination and TNC channel**

207 The structures of laccases Pa5930/Pp4816 show one copper ion bound at the T1Cu site
208 and three copper ions bound at the trinuclear copper center (TNC), which are distributed
209 as one copper ion bound to the T2Cu site and a pair bound to T3Cu site (Fig. 5A). Copper
210 coordination at the T1Cu site and the TNC is similar to CueO and CotA (Fig. S6A). The
211 T1Cu site is located close to the protein surface at domain 3 and is coordinated by four
212 residues His389/391, His448/450, Cys443/445, and Met453/455. In turn, the T1Cu site
213 is connected to the TNC, which is buried at the interface of domain 1 and 3, through two
214 adjacent His bound to the pair of coppers at the T3Cu site (Figs. 5A and S6A). As in other

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3 215 laccases, the TNC is surrounded by conserved negative residues Glu449/451, Asp116/118
4
5 216 and Asp417/419 (Fig. S6B), which have been proposed to facilitate oxygen binding and
6
7 217 to supply protons for the reduction of oxygen. Glu seems to play a crucial role (Chen, *et*
8
9 218 *al.* 2010, Komori, *et al.* 2012) as it is connected to T1Cu site through the adjacent His
10
11 219 (Fig. S6B). Interestingly, water molecules could be modelled in the structures interacting
12
13 220 with the TNC, one located between T3aCu and T3bCu sites and the other interacting with
14
15 221 T2Cu (Fig. 5A). The presence of these water molecules at the TNC site was indicative of
16
17 222 a reduced form, which could be acquired upon exposure to X-rays as evidenced in
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19 223 structural studies of CueO (Komori, *et al.* 2014).

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24 224 Additionally, in the Pa5930 and Pp4816 structures, waters were modelled that define the
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26 225 channel leading to the TNC. The 32-residue C-terminal extension in Pp4816 caps this
27
28 226 channel and appears to restrict access to it (Fig. S7). Several residues (Y502, M509, and
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30 227 M476), as well as the C-terminal carboxyl group, project into the entrance of the TNC
31
32 228 channel (Fig. 5B). Pa5930 lacks this extension and has a much more exposed TNC (Fig.
33
34 229 5C). A search of all laccase crystal structures revealed none have significant sequence
35
36 230 similarity to the Pp4816 C-terminus; however, the *Melanocarpus albomyces* MaL laccase
37
38 231 presents a conserved “C-terminal plug” that occupies the TNC channel (Hakulinen, *et al.*
39
40 232 2002). Although MaL has significant structural differences to Pp4816 before this point,
41
42 233 both C-termini arrive at the TNC channel, with MaL’s C-terminal plug more deeply
43
44 234 penetrating the channel (Fig. 5D).

235 **Substrate binding site**

236 In order to trap *Pediococcus* laccases bound to substrate, co-crystallization and soaking
237 studies were performed with Pa5930 laccase. Substrates used were ABTS, tyramine, and
238 dopamine either alone or in complex. No substrate-bound was found at the laccase

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3 239 structures even after direct addition to the crystals of a concentrated 100 mM stock
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5 240 solution or pure substrate.
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8 241 Many laccases feature acidic pH optima. As Pa5930 structures were solved at basic pH
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10 242 (8.5 and 7.5), where Pa5930 laccase has little activity for tyramine, a second
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12 243 crystallization condition was found at pH 3.0, and the structure was determined to 1.8 Å
13
14 244 (Table 3). Common laccase substrates (Table S2) were soaked into crystals or co-
15
16 245 crystallized at 10 mM final concentration. Co-crystallization frequently resulted in low-
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18 246 resolution or mosaic data, but several complete data sets were obtained. No additional
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20 247 electron density was observed for any of these substrates. Interestingly, crystals at pH 3.0
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22 248 belonged to the monoclinic space group $P2_1$ and feature two molecules in the asymmetric
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24 249 unit, in contrast to crystals at basic pH that belong to the orthorhombic space group
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26 250 $P2_12_12_1$ with one molecule in the asymmetric unit. At pH 3.0, the two molecules produced
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28 251 a dimeric interface stabilized by a benzamidine molecule which was essential for
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30 252 crystallization (Fig. S8). The dimeric interface is an artifact of crystal packing since
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32 253 Pa5930 was determined to be monomeric by gel filtration chromatography (data not
33
34 254 shown) and the PISA server (Krissinel and Henrick 2007) ruled out its stability in
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36 255 solution. The structures of Pa5930 at acidic and basic pH were almost identical with an
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38 256 RMSD of ~ 0.3 Å, aside from some slight variation in loop regions involved in crystal
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40 257 packing. The structure at acidic pH also allowed modelling three additional residues at
41
42 258 the C-terminus. The acidic pH-dependent activity of Pa5930 is, therefore, not mediated
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44 259 by major structural changes. Instead, it may be determined by protonation of key residues
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46 260 or the inherent increase in redox potential with decreasing pH (Brissos, *et al.* 2012).
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55 261 As efforts to obtain structures of *Pediococcus* laccases bound to substrates were not
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57 262 successful, we superposed Pa5930 and Pp4816 with CotA structures deposited in the PDB
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59 263 bound to the substrates ABTS (PDB: 1OF0 and 4YVN) and sinapic acid (4Q8B) (Fig.
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3 264 6A). Interestingly, CotA can bind ABTS on two different sites, one site (PDB: 3ZDW
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5 265 and 1OF0) is similar to sinapic acid binding (PDB: 4Q8B). This binding site is rather
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7 266 conserved in fungal laccases (PDB: 2HRG) and as it lies in domain 3, specifically at the
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9 267 entrance of T1Cu site (Enguita, *et al.* 2004) (Fig. 6B), it is proposed to be the active site
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11 268 where substrate oxidation can be mediated (Mehra, *et al.* 2018). The other binding site
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13 269 for ABTS in CotA (PDB: 4YVN) lies in the long coil region that connects domains 2 and
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15 270 3 (Liu, *et al.* 2016) (Fig. 6C). The structural superposition with *Pediococcus* laccases
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17 271 reveals that there would be clashes for substrate binding without a change in
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19 272 conformation, but more importantly, the entrance of the T1Cu site is occluded by
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21 273 Met347/350 and Met387/389 (Fig. 6D). This feature is also observed in CueO where the
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23 274 methionine-rich region blocks physical access to the T1Cu site (Cortes, *et al.* 2015) (Fig.
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25 275 S9). In this way, substrate binding at laccases Pa5930/Pp4816 might require
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27 276 conformational changes for the opening of the entrance at the T1Cu site or the presence
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29 277 of alternative binding sites.
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36 278 **DISCUSSION**

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38 279 The amino acid sequence of laccase Pp4816 places this enzyme into the subfamily J
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40 280 (bacterial CueO proteins) of the multicopper oxidases group (according to the Laccase
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42 281 Engineering Database) (Sirim, *et al.* 2011), the same group that includes CueO from *E.*
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44 282 *coli* and the *L. plantarum* J16 and Pa5930 laccases. Moreover, the characteristic UV-
45
46 283 Visible spectrum with an absorption peak at 600 nm, the blue color, and the ability to
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48 284 oxidize typical laccase substrates of the Pp4816 enzyme confirm it is a genuine laccase.
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50 285 Pp4816 and Pa5930 contain the four strictly conserved copper ligand motifs
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52 286 characteristics of MCO enzymes (Fig. 1) including consensus His residues, a typical trait
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54 287 of classical laccases (Fernandes, *et al.* 2014, Kumar, *et al.* 2016). Pp4816 and Pa5930
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56 288 have a relatively high sequence identity (59%); however, Pp4816 is closer related to the
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3 289 *L. plantarum* J16 laccase (66% identity) described by Callejón, *et al.* (2016). It was not
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5 290 possible to estimate the percentage of identity of laccase Pp4816 with that of *L. fermentum*
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7 291 Y29 MCO recently published, since its gene sequence was not included in the report (nor
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9 292 could it be deduced from the primers described) (Xu and Fang 2019).

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11 293 The optimal pH of Pp4816 recombinant laccase acting on the non-phenolic substrate
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13 294 ABTS is acidic (pH 3.5), similar to that of other bacterial laccases, which ranges between
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15 295 2.5 to 5.0 (Chauhan, *et al.* 2017). Thermostability assays showed that Pp4816 enzyme is
16
17 296 more resistant to high temperatures than Pa5930 and less thermostable than *L. plantarum*
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19 297 J16 laccase, as *L. plantarum* J16 maintains 60% activity or more up to 100°C. High
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21 298 thermal stabilities have been reported from various recombinant laccases: *Thermus*
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23 299 *thermophilus* SG0.5JP17-16, CotA from *B. subtilis*, *Bacillus vallismortis* fmb-103, and
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25 300 *Bacillus licheniformis* laccases (Martins, *et al.* 2002, Lu, *et al.* 2013, Liu, *et al.* 2015, Sun,
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27 301 *et al.* 2017). An amazing characteristic of Pp4816 laccase is that its activity was enhanced
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29 302 after pre-incubation in a temperature range between 28 and 75°C, reaching 50% more
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31 303 activity after 10 min at 65°C pre-incubation than after 10 min at 28°C. This behavior
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33 304 could be speculatively explained because at high temperatures the protein structure
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35 305 undergoes conformational changes that will permit better substrate access to the active
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37 306 site, a Cu centers reorganizes, or inactive molecules refold. Similar behavior was noted
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39 307 for the laccase of *L. plantarum* J16 (Callejón, *et al.* 2016) and a number of other bacterial
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41 308 and fungal laccases (Mohammadian, *et al.* 2010).

42
43 309 Strikingly, our kinetic analyses have revealed that both Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases
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45 310 exhibit sigmoidal kinetics for the artificial non-phenolic substrate ABTS, which, to our
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47 311 knowledge, had not previously been reported for any other laccase. Generally,
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49 312 sigmoidicity of rate curves results of a cooperative effect in the substrate binding by
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51 313 multimeric enzymes (Cornish-Bowden 2012); however we have not found any evidence
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3 314 for an oligomeric structure in our crystallographic studies, nor in our size exclusion
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5 315 chromatography analyses, so apparently both recombinant laccases are monomeric
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7 316 proteins. Although rare, sigmoidal kinetics can also occur in monomeric enzymes, either
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9 317 reflecting substrate binding to an effector site in addition to a single active center, or by
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11 318 a hysteretic mechanism, that is, substrate binding to an enzyme with different
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13 319 conformations (Porter and Miller 2012). We have not obtained crystals of any
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15 320 *Pediococcus* laccase containing ABTS bound, but since the homologous enzyme CotA is
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17 321 known to bind ABTS at a second site (Enguita, *et al.* 2004), the first of the above
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19 322 mechanisms is plausible. In any case, further studies will be required to refine the peculiar
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21 323 behavior of *Pediococcus* laccases regarding the artificial substrate ABTS, and their
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23 324 physiological function, if any, acting on natural substrates. $K_{0.5}$ values for both Pp4816
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25 325 and Pa5930 recombinant enzymes with ABTS were similar to the K_m previously
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27 326 determined for the *L. plantarum* J16 laccase (Callejón, *et al.* 2016), although lower than
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29 327 the K_m of the recently described *L. fermentum* Y29 (Xu and Fang 2019). Thus, apparently,
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31 328 the affinity of *Pediococcus* laccases for ABTS is higher than that of *L. plantarum* and *L.*
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33 329 *fermentum* laccases.

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40 330 Low percentages of inhibition of 100 μ M EDTA, EDC, bipyridyl, and phenanthroline on
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42 331 Pa5930 laccase were recorded by Callejón, *et al.* (2016). However, when 1 mM of these
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44 332 and other compounds was tested in the present study on both Pp4816 and Pa5930
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46 333 recombinant enzymes, higher percentages of inhibition were observed. The most effective
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48 334 inhibitory compounds were reducing agents, such as cysteine, electron transfer blockers
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50 335 to oxygen, such as azide, and also covalent modifying compounds typical of monoamine
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52 336 oxidases, such as semicarbazide. *Pediococcus* laccases feature inhibition similar to other
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54 337 diverse laccases (Singh, *et al.* 2011, Callejón, *et al.* 2016, Callejón, *et al.* 2017).
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3 338 The new potential application, recently described, for laccase enzymes in the elimination
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5 339 of toxic biogenic amines (BA) in food has increased interest in LAB laccases, since LAB
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7 340 strains are frequently found in food. We have previously shown that the laccase of *L.*
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9 341 *plantarum* J16, a LAB strain isolated from wine, can degrade different BA (Callejón, *et*
10
11 342 *al.* 2016). We have found that both LAB Pp4816 and Pa5930 recombinant laccases
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13 343 catalyze the oxidation of dopamine and tyramine, but not histamine, phenylethylamine,
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15 344 or putrescine. Apparently, a phenolic structure, present in dopamine and tyramine, is
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17 345 required to be a suitable substrate. Although the *L. plantarum* J16 laccase showed low
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19 346 activity on the N-heterocycle histamine, and on the aliphatic diamine putrescine, tyramine
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21 347 was by far the best substrate (Callejón, *et al.* 2016). Together, these results indicate that
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23 348 just as phenolic compounds are generally better substrates for both fungal and bacterial
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25 349 laccases (Reiss, *et al.* 2013), phenolic amines are also better for LAB laccases.
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27 350 Nevertheless, with both recombinant laccases, Pp4816, and Pa5930, and under the assay
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29 351 conditions used in this work, efficient tyramine oxidation required the presence of ABTS
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31 352 as a redox mediator. Dopamine was significantly oxidized in the absence of a mediator,
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33 353 although in the presence of ABTS its degradation was increased. The distinct suitability
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35 354 as a substrate for these aromatic amines could be the result of the additional -OH group
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37 355 adjacent to the phenoxy-OH in dopamine. In this regard, has been reported (for many
38
39 356 different laccases) that the oxidizing activity is higher on phenolic substrates containing
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41 357 one or more hydroxy or methoxy group(s), with a lone pair of electrons, adjacent to the
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43 358 phenol (Reiss, *et al.* 2011, Reiss, *et al.* 2013). The laccase from *L. fermentum* Y29 has
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45 359 extended abilities to degrade BA; thus, it degrades histamine, tyramine, putrescine, and
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47 360 spermidine in a similar range between 40-50%, and apparently in absence of any mediator
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49 361 compound (Xu and Fang 2019). This high oxidizing capability on non-aromatic BA is
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51 362 surprising, considering that for most laccases the typical substrate is aromatic. Further
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3 363 work and a deeper analysis are required to understand entirely this apparently
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5 364 extraordinary laccase enzyme.
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8 365 The structural analysis of *Pediococcus* laccases Pa5930 and Pp4816 have shown that they
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10 366 share similarity with other laccases such as CotA and CueO, having three cupredoxin-
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12 367 like domains and coordinating four Cu ions comprised at the T1Cu and TNC sites.
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14 368 However, the structures have revealed an extension of the C-terminus, absent in CotA
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16 369 and CueO, which is 32-residues longer in Pp4816 than Pa5930. Moreover, the C-terminal
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18 370 extension in both *Pediococcus* laccases contains a high percentage of Met and His,
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20 371 especially in Pp4816, where five Met form a hydrophobic patch that is surface exposed.
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22 372 This feature is rather common among LAB (Fig. 1), where some show a longer C-
23
24 373 terminus rich in His. In general, all LAB laccases share a rather common general
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26 374 sequence, even those more distantly related (Fig. 1), indicating the C-terminus is a
27
28 375 distinctive character among them. These C-terminal sequences are rather rich in Met
29
30 376 and/or His, which could have a specific role *in vivo* to be determined. The presence of
31
32 377 this Met/His rich region could be involved in additional copper-binding as a substrate
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34 378 docking-oxidation site for the cuprous oxidase function, as observed in CueO (Cortes, *et*
35
36 379 *al.* 2015), or in sequestration and transport of copper as in the copper pump CusA (Su, *et*
37
38 380 *al.* 2011). Indeed, in Pa5930 and Pp4816, the conserved binding site for the substrate that
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40 381 lies at the entrance of the T1Cu site, present in CotA and other fungal laccases (Mehra, *et*
41
42 382 *al.* 2018), is occupied by two Met contributing to a reduced substrate binding affinity. In
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44 383 fact, no substrate was found at the laccase structures despite many trials of soaking, and
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46 384 co-crystallization studies with different substrates were performed. However, the fact that
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48 385 the Met hydrophobic patch, as observed in Pp4816, is far away from the T1Cu site (~15Å)
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50 386 contrasts with its function as an electron-transfer mediator.
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3 387 Our structural studies have also revealed that in Pp4816, the water channel leading to the
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5 388 TNC is capped by the C-terminal extension, similarly (but less pronounced than) the
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7 389 ascomycete laccase MaL. C-terminal extensions have been found to modulate the activity
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10 390 of several laccases, indeed, truncation of the final four residues of MaL, or mutation of
11
12 391 Leu559 (the final residue) to Ala significantly impairs activity (Andberg, *et al.* 2009).
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14 392 Consistent with these results, compared to Pa5930, Pp4816 shows higher thermostability,
15
16 393 a slightly more acidic pH optimum, a bit higher activity against tyramine with mediators,
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18 394 and twice the activity against dopamine without mediators. Conversely, in the
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21 395 *Myceliophthora thermophila* laccase, which also has conserved ascomycete C-terminal
22
23 396 plug (Ernst, *et al.* 2018), mutation of a conserved Ser (which appears to form a hydrogen
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25 397 bond with the C-terminal plug) to Gly resulted in an increase in activity towards phenolic
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27 398 (8-fold) and non-phenolic (3-fold) substrates (Zumarraga, *et al.* 2008). Mutation or
28
29 399 truncation of the C-terminal residues of *Basidiomycetes* laccases also affects their activity
30
31 400 (Pardo and Camarero 2015) , having been associated with protein processing, stability,
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33 401 and activity, but not regulation of access to the TNC channel. The presence of the
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35 402 C-terminal plug in Pp4816 restricting access to the TNC could be involved in modulating
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37 403 its laccase activity. A similar situation could happen for other laccases possessing similar
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39 404 or longer C-terminal chains rich in His (Figs. 1 and S4). Thus, function and impact on the
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41 405 activity of the C-terminal Met/His rich extension of these *Pediococcus* laccases as well
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43 406 as influence of the C-terminal plug are yet to be determined.
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408 **EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES**

409 **Chemicals and DNA and protein purification systems**

410 2,2-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS), 2,6-dimethoxyphenol
411 (2,6-DMP), 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HBT), tyramine, dopamine, phenylethylamine,

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3 412 putrescine, N-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC), 1,10-
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5 413 phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl, clorgyline, cyclopropylamine, deprenyl, pargyline HCl,
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7 414 rasagiline, semicarbazide, NaCl, NaF and molecular weight standard proteins were
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9 415 obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine 1-oxyl free
10
11 416 radical (TEMPO) was from TCI (Tokyo, Japan). Nickel-chelating nitrilotriacetic acid
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13 417 (Ni^{+2} -NTA) agarose was from Qiagen (Hilden, Germany). All other chemicals and
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15 418 reagents were of analytical grade.

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19 419 Restriction enzymes were obtained from New England Biolabs (Beverly, MA), T4 DNA
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21 420 ligase was from Roche Diagnostics (Barcelona, Spain) and DNA polymerase was from
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23 421 Invitrogen (La Jolla, CA).
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25 422 The UltraClean® PCR Clean-Up kit (Metabion) and the NZyMiniprep kit (Nzytech) were
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27 423 used. DNA synthetic oligonucleotides were from Eurofins MWG Operon (Ebersberg,
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29 424 Germany).

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34 35 426 **Strains, plasmids, and proteins**

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37 427 *P. pentosaceus* 4816 strain was isolated from pasta manufacturing process.

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39 428 *Escherichia coli* DH5 α was used for cloning, amplification, and propagation of the
40
41 429 putative laccase gene. *E. coli* BL21(DE3) (Novagen), also harbors the pGro7 plasmid
42
43 430 (kindly provided by R. Muñoz from ICTAN-CSIC) coding the genes of chaperones
44
45 431 (groES-groEL), that cooperatively help the protein folding process (Thomas, *et al.* 1997).

46
47 432 The plasmid pET-28a(+) was from Novagen (Madison, WI, USA). Pa5930 purified
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49 433 laccase was previously obtained by Callejón *et al.* (Callejón, *et al.* 2017), but a new
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51 434 purification was carried out for this work.

52 53 54 55 435 **Growth conditions**

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3 436 *P. pentosaceus* 4816 was routinely cultivated in MRS medium (Scharlau S.L., Barcelona,
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5 437 Spain) at 28°C. *E. coli* cells were grown at 37°C in Luria–Bertani (LB) medium
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7 438 (Sambrook, *et al.* 1989), and transformants, when appropriate, were grown in LB medium
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9
10 439 supplemented with 50 µg mL⁻¹ kanamycin or with kanamycin plus 20 µg mL⁻¹ of
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12 440 chloramphenicol.

14 441 **Cloning of the gene encoding the Pp4816 laccase, construction of the expression** 15 16 17 442 **plasmid, and expression conditions**

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19 443 The Pp4816 laccase gene was amplified by PCR from purified genomic DNA with newly
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21 444 designed primers LacaPepe1 (5'-GAT**GCTAGCAT**GAAAACTATACGGACTATTT-
22
23 445 3') and LacaPepe2 (5'-CCG**GAATTCTT**TACATTTTCATTCCCATTTT-3').
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25
26 446 Recognition sites for NheI and EcoRI, at the start and end of the codifying sequence, are
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28 447 indicated in bold italics. The thermal profile setup was as in (Callejón, *et al.* 2017). All
29
30 448 the next molecular manipulations were done as described in (Callejón, *et al.* 2017). The
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32 449 recombinant laccase was cloned in pET-28a to obtain the plasmid pET-28a-Pp4816.

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36 450 The expression of the two laccases was done as in (Callejón, *et al.* 2017), using here 0.5
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38 451 mg mL⁻¹ of arabinose, and 0.2 mM of CuCl₂.

41 452 **Recombinant laccase purification**

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45 453 Frozen cells recovered from 2 liters culture were thawed and lysed as in (Callejón, *et al.*
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47 454 2017) but including one cOmplete™ Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet (Merck) (Smith
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49 455 1985). The activity of different fractions was determined in the standard reaction buffer
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51 456 (SRB): 100 mM sodium acetate, 0.1 mM CuSO₄, pH 4.0, and including 2 mM ABTS as
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53 457 substrate (Callejón, *et al.* 2014). The rest of the steps were done as described in (Callejón,
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55
56 458 *et al.* 2017).

59 459 **Biochemical characterization of Pp4816 laccase**

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3 460 The UV–visible absorption spectra (300–800 nm) of the pure recombinant Pp4816
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5 461 laccase was performed as in (Callejón, *et al.* 2017).
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9 462 The relative molecular mass of the denatured protein was determined by comparison with
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11 463 the migration positions of the molecular mass markers (Spectra Multicolor Marker
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13 464 (Thermo Scientific) in an SDS-7.5% PAGE.
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16 465 Kinetic parameters of Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases were determined at room temperature
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18 466 (24°C) using different concentrations of ABTS (0.01-2 mM) or the alternative laccase
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20 467 substrates, potassium ferrocyanide (0.1-2 mM), and 2,6-DMP (0.4-10 mM). Assays with
21
22 468 ABTS and ferrocyanide were carried out in 50 mM sodium citrate buffer, pH 3.4, and
23
24 469 reactions were followed by registering OD₄₂₀ on a Beckman Coulter DU800 UV/Vis
25
26 470 spectrophotometer. With 2,6-DMP, 50 mM Tris·HCl buffer, pH 7.2 was used, and its
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28 471 oxidation was determined by the OD₄₆₈ increase. Previously the linear dependence of the
29
30 472 enzymatic activity with recombinant enzyme concentration was checked. Reactions were
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32 473 performed in a total volume of 600 µL and were initiated by the addition of the enzymes.
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34 474 The steady-state reaction rates were obtained from the initial slope of the linear section
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36 475 after plotting OD versus time. All determinations were carried out at least in triplicates
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38 476 and also with different final concentrations of the recombinant laccases, in particular,
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40 477 between 0.05 and 0.2 µg mL⁻¹ with ABTS; between 1.66 and 3.33 µg mL⁻¹ with
41
42 478 ferrocyanide; and 20-80 µg mL⁻¹ with 2,6-DPM. Enzyme activity is expressed in units
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44 479 (U), defined as the amount of active enzyme that oxidizes 1 µmol of substrate min⁻¹. The
45
46 480 extinction coefficients used, corresponding to the oxidation products, were: ABTS, ε₄₂₀=
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48 481 36000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹; K₄[Fe(CN)₆], ε₄₂₀=880 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹; and 2,6-DMP, ε₄₆₈= 14800 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹.
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56 482 Activity of Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases on HBT and TEMPO, as potential substrates,
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58 483 was tested as described by Ander and Messner (1998) and Kulys and Vidziunaite (2005),
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1
2
3 484 respectively. The assays were carried out, with the recombinant laccases at a final
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5 485 concentration of $30 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, in two different buffers: 50 mM sodium citrate, pH 4.0, and
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7 486 50 mM Tris·H₂SO₄, pH 7.5. In these assays, commercial *Trametes versicolor* laccase
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9 487 (Sigma), at $3 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, was used as a positive activity control. ABTS, HBT and TEMPO
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11 488 were also tested as mediators of both laccases for the oxidation of 2,6-DMP at pH 4.0.
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13 489 For these trials, the reaction mixtures contained $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of enzyme, 4 mM 2,6-DMP,
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15 490 and 0.5 mM of the potential mediators in sodium citrate buffer, pH 4.0. 2,6-DMP
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17 491 oxidation was followed by DO₄₆₈. Samples in which any mediator was omitted were
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19 492 negative controls.

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24 493 To determine the effect of pH on laccase activity with ABTS (2 mM), 2,6-DMP (4 mM)
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26 494 and guaiacol (40 mM) as substrates, a 50 mM citrate-phosphate buffer, 0.1 mM CuSO₄,
27
28 495 was used, covering a pH range from 2.5 to 9.0. Final laccase concentration was $5,5 \mu\text{g}$
29
30 496 mL^{-1} with ABTS; and $36.6 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with 2,6-DMP and guaiacol. Enzyme activity on these
31
32 497 substrates was determined spectrophotometrically at an OD₄₂₀ for ABTS and guaiacol
33
34 498 and OD₄₆₈ for 2,6-DMP during 30 min incubation at room temperature. The effect of
35
36 499 temperature on Pp4816 laccase activity in the range 20 to 100°C was checked by
37
38 500 measuring ABTS oxidation using 200 μL of SRB plus 2 mM ABTS to which 1 μL of an
39
40 501 enzyme solution of ($365 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was added. The reaction medium was pre-incubated
41
42 502 for 5 min at the corresponding temperatures before the addition of the recombinant
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44 503 enzyme. For thermal stability analysis, 200 μL of SRB plus 10 μL of an enzyme solution
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46 504 ($91 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was pre-incubated at the different temperatures ranging from 28 to 85°C for
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48 505 5 min. After recovering the room temperature, reactions were initiated by the inclusion
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50 506 of ABTS at the final concentration of 2 mM.
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3 507 **In temperature** and thermal stability analyses, reactions were developed for 3 min then
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5 508 stopped by adding sodium azide to a final concentration of 1 mM. Oxidation of ABTS
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7 509 was measured by recording the increase of OD₄₂₀ **in microplate wells.**

510 **Effect of putative inhibitor compounds on Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases**

511 The effect of metal-chelating agents 2,2'-bipyridyl, and EDTA; compounds affecting the
512 oxidizing potential of the enzyme clorgyline, cyclopropylamine, deprenyl, EDC,
513 pargyline, phenanthroline, rasagiline, semicarbazide, and sodium azide; **halides such as**
514 **sodium fluoride and chloride, which bind to the T2 copper prohibiting oxygen from being**
515 **reduced;** and reducing agents cysteine and thioglycolic acid, and also Zn²⁺, with potential
516 for substitution of Cu²⁺, provided as zinc chloride, was tested on the recombinant laccase
517 Pp4816 similarly as was previously examined on Pa5930 laccase (Callejón, *et al.* 2017).
518 After incubating 10 µL of a 183 µg mL⁻¹ enzyme solution with 190 µL SRB plus 1 mM
519 inhibitor for 10 min, reaction was initiated by the addition of ABTS (2 mM final
520 concentration) and let to progress for 3 min when was stopped by adding sodium azide to
521 a final concentration of 1 mM. Oxidation of ABTS was measured by recording the
522 increase of OD₄₂₀ in microplate wells. The value from a reaction without inhibitor was
523 considered as 100 % relative enzyme activity (control).

524 **Activity of Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases on biogenic amines**

525 Histamine, tyramine, putrescine, dopamine, and phenylethylamine, in the presence and
526 absence of the mediator ABTS, were tested as potential substrates. Incubations were
527 carried out with 100 µL of SRB containing the amine at a final concentration of 150 µg
528 mL⁻¹, and in the presence/absence of 2 mM ABTS. **Pa5930 and Pp4816 concentrations in**
529 **the reaction mix were 33.76 and 29.9 µg mL⁻¹, respectively.** Reaction mixtures were
530 incubated at 28°C for 24 hours, after which the remaining amine concentration was

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3 531 determined by LC-FLD (Callejón, *et al.* 2016). As negative controls, mixtures without
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5 532 enzyme or with a heat-inactivated enzyme (100°C for 10 min) were tested under identical
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7 533 conditions.
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10 534 **Crystallization, data collection, model building, and analysis**

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14 535 For crystallization of laccase Pa5930, first, gel filtration was performed in 50 mM Tris-
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16 536 HCl pH 7.5 and 250 mM NaCl using a ProteoSEC 6-600 kDa HR column (Generon).
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18 537 Different fractions were collected and run in a 12% SDS-PAGE gel, then, were
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20 538 concentrated with Vivaspin 20 concentrators (Sartorius). Crystals of Pa5930 were
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22 539 prepared at the IBV-CSIC Crystallogenesi Facility by the sitting drop vapor diffusion
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24 540 crystallization technique at 21°C, mixing 0.3 μL of protein solution at 10 mg mL^{-1} with
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26 541 0.3 μL of different reservoir solutions. The best diffracting crystals were grown and
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28 542 cryoprotected in the conditions shown in Table 3. Crystals of Pp4680 and Pa5930 at pH
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30 543 3.0 were prepared at the NSLS II acoustic sample preparation facility. An Echo™
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32 544 (Labcyte) was used to assemble hanging-drop vapor diffusion crystal trials on 3D printed
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34 545 tray (Soares, *et al.* 2018) from aliquots of solutions in a source plate. Pp4816 formed
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36 546 crystals overnight at 20°C in a 60 nL drop. The largest single crystals were obtained with
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38 547 protein serially diluted from 20 mg mL^{-1} in water (final conditions in Table 3). Mylar was
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40 548 used as the tray surface, and 2 M lithium sulfate was the reservoir solution. Pa5930 (pH
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42 549 3.0) also crystallized in a combinatorial screen at 5-15 mg mL^{-1} , with a tray reservoir
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44 550 solution of 15% PEG8000 and 15% PEG400. Mylar was initially used as the surface,
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46 551 resulting in micro-polycrystalline needles. Changing the surface to COC (cyclic olefin
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48 552 copolymer) resulted in large high-quality single crystals.
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54 553 Diffraction of Pa5930 crystals at basic pH was performed under cryogenic conditions at
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56 554 beamline I24 at Diamond Light Source Synchrotron (DLS, Didcot, UK) and BL13-
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3 555 XALOC at Spanish Synchrotron Radiation Facility ALBA (ALBA, Cerdanyola del
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5 556 Vallès, Spain) while diffraction of Pp4816 and Pa5930 at pH 3 crystals was performed
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7 557 under cryogenic conditions at 17-ID-1 (AMX) at NSLS-II. Crystallographic data
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9 558 collected at the Diamond light source were processed with the XDS Program Package
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11 559 (Kabsch 2010) and scaled with the program AIMLESS from the Collaborative
12
13 560 Computational Project, Number 4, CCP4 suite (Winn, *et al.* 2011). Data collected at the
14
15 561 NSLS-II was indexed and scaled with *FastDP* (Winter and McAuley 2011). For phasing,
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17 562 molecular replacement was conducted using Phaser (McCoy, *et al.* 2007) and CotA
18
19 563 (PDB: 3ZDW) as the search model. The final structure was obtained upon iterative cycles
20
21 564 of tracing and refinement using COOT (Emsley, *et al.* 2010) and Refmac5 (Murshudov,
22
23 565 *et al.* 2011), respectively. Details of the data-collection and refinement are shown in **Table**
24
25 566 **3**. To note, Pa5930 crystals soaked with substrate proved to be more resistant during
26
27 567 incubation in crystals grown at pH 7.5. Superpositions were produced with program
28
29 568 Superpose in the CCP4 Suite. Figures were produced using UCSF Chimera (Pettersen, *et*
30
31 569 *al.* 2004).

37 38 570 **Data availability**

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41 571 The X-ray crystallographic coordinates for the laccase structures have been deposited at
42
43 572 the Protein Data Bank with the following accession codes; Pa5930 at pH 8.5 as 6Z0J, at
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45 573 pH 7.5 as 6Z0K and pH 3.0 as 6XJ0 and Pp4816 as 6XIZ.

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3 575 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**
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14
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17 581 synchrotrons, respectively, for providing assistance during data collection. X-ray
18
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37 591 for this study were collected at 17-ID-1 (AMX) of the National Synchrotron Light Source
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3 599 **CONFLICT OF INTERESTS**
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601 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

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603 FIG 1: Multiple sequence alignment and conservation scoring of the *L. plantarum* J16,
604 *Lactobacillus apis*-52100, *Lactococcus lactis*-9504, Pa5930, and Pp4816 laccases using
605 Praline software (Bawono and Heringa 2014). The sequences of *L. apis* and *L. lactis* are
606 representative of longest and shortest C-terminus groups in LAB, surrounded respectively
607 in red and grey in Fig. S4. The scoring scheme works from 0 for the least conserved
608 alignment position, up to 10 for the most conserved alignment position, the identical
609 conserved residues are indicated by asterisks (color scale indicated on top). Dashes
610 indicate gaps to maximize alignment. Encased inside boxes are the motifs that form the
611 four copper ligands and are highly conserved in laccases (conserved sequence of these
612 motifs are HXHG, HXH, HXXHXX, and HCHXXXHXXXM/L/F (Sharma, *et al.*
613 2007). C-terminal Met residues are highlighted in yellow, and His in purple.

614

615 FIG 2: Purification and biochemical characterization of Pp4816 laccase from *P.*
616 *pentosaceus*. (A) Aliquots of the fractions from the different purification steps of the
617 Pp4816 laccase were analyzed by PageBlue-stained 7.5% SDS-polyacrylamide gel
618 electrophoresis. Lane M1, Amersham™ ECL™ Rainbow™ Marker - Full range; lanes 1-
619 8, consecutive fractions obtained after elution of the bound proteins from the Ni⁺²-NTA
620 agarose matrix; lane 9, column washing fraction; lane 10, unbound proteins collected in
621 the flow-through; lane 11, crude cell extract, corresponding to the loaded sample on the
622 column; lane 12, whole-cell proteins from an induced culture; lane 13, whole-cell proteins
623 from a non-induced culture; and lane M2, Pierce™ Prestained Protein MW Marker. (B)
624 UV-Visible spectrum of purified recombinant Pp4816 laccase in 50 mM sodium
625 phosphate, pH 6.5 buffer. Only the range 350-800 nm wavelength is shown. (C) pH effect

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3 626 on the activity of the Pp4816 enzyme toward ABTS (filled circle) and 2,6-DMP (filled
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5 627 square). Enzyme activity is plotted as a percentage relative to the maximum value (%
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8 628 relative activity). The values are means \pm standard deviations from triplicate assays. (D)
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10 629 Temperature dependence and (E) T_{50} of the Pp4816 laccase are determined against ABTS.
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12 630 In D, the maximum value was assumed as 100% activity and the others were calculated
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14 631 proportionally. In E, relative activities were calculated considering the OD₄₂₀ increase
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16 632 obtained at 28°C as 100% activity; the resulting percentages are plotted against the
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18 633 pretreatment temperature. The values are means \pm standard deviations from triplicate
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20 634 assays.
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26 636 FIG 3: Effect of different putative inhibitors on Pp4816 (green) and Pa5930 (orange)
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28 637 laccases. EDC: N-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl)-N'-ethyl carbodiimide; Phenan.: 1,10-
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30 638 phenanthroline; Cyclop.: cyclopropenyl; Depren.: deprenyl; Clorgyl.: clorgyline;
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32 639 Semicarb.: semicarbazide; Rasag.: rasagiline; Parg.: pargyline ; Bipy.: 2,2'-bipyridyl ;
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34 640 Thio. ac.: thioglycolic acid; Na Az.: sodium azide; ZnCl₂: zinc chloride; Cys.: cysteine
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36 641 HCl monohydrate; EDTA: ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; NaCl: sodium chloride; NaF:
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38 642 sodium fluoride; Control means an enzyme assay in absence of inhibitors. The remaining
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40 643 activity with the different potential inhibitors is graphed as percentage respect to the
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42 644 control (assumed as 100% of enzyme activity). Values are means \pm standard deviations
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44 645 of triplicate assays.
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51 647 FIG 4: Structure of *Pediococcus* laccases Pa5930 and Pp4816. (A) Structural
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53 648 superposition of both *Pediococcus* laccases with each cupredoxin-like domain color-
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55 649 coded (1 in cyan, 2 in yellow, and 3 in magenta). The long coil region connecting domain
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57 650 2 with 3 is colored in red and the C-terminal extension of Pp416 is colored in pale orange.
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3 651 The four copper ions are shown as yellow spheres. (B) Surface representation of domains
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5 652 2 and cartoon representation of domain 1, all domains are color-coded. (C) Superposition
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7 653 of each cupredoxin domain at *Pediococcus* laccases Pa5930 (in blue) and Pp4816 (in pale
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9 654 orange) together with CotA of *B. subtilis* (in magenta, PDB: 3ZDW) and CueO of *E. coli*
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11 655 (in green, PDB: 4E9T). (D) C-terminal sequence alignment of *Pediococcus* laccases
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13 656 highlighting the presence of Met (in yellow) and His (in purple) residues.
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19 658 FIG 5. Copper coordination and TNC channel. (A) View of the T1 Cu and TNC site of
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21 659 coordination for superposed Pa5930 and Pp4816 laccases. Cu ions (in yellow) and water
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23 660 molecules at the TNC (W, in red) are rendered as spheres. The coordinating residues are
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25 661 color-coded (blue for Pa5930 and pale orange for Pp4816). The cartoon represents
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27 662 domain 1 (in cyan) and domain 3 (in magenta), which scaffold the copper-binding motifs.
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29 663 The electron density map around the Cu ions is contoured at 1σ . (B) Detail of C-terminal
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31 664 extension of Pp4816 (orange) that caps and inserts several residues into the TNC channel
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33 665 (C) Pa5930 (blue) lacks this C-terminal extension and has a more exposed TNC. (D)
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35 666 Ascomycete laccases' C-terminal plugs (PDB 1GW0, rendered gray), penetrate the TNC
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37 667 channel in a similar location as Pp4816's C-terminus. Waters observed in the Pa5930 and
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39 668 Pp4816 crystal structures leading to the TNC are modelled as red spheres.
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49 670 FIG 6: Analysis of the substrate binding site in CotA with the Pa5930 and Pp4816
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51 671 laccases (A) Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue) with CotA (in yellow) showing the two
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53 672 binding sites for ABTS (represented in atoms and transparent surface in orange). The long
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55 673 coil region connecting domain 2 with 3 is colored in red in both structures. (B) Closeup
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57 674 of ABTS binding at the T1Cu site, the conserved laccase active site. Pa5930 shows
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59 675 clashes with ABTS bound to CotA. (C) Closeup of ABTS binding at an alternative site in
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3 676 CotA, located at the long coil region (in red) which also shows clashes with Pa5930. (D)

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5 677 Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue) and Pp4816 (in pale orange) laccases showing Met

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8 678 residues that lie at the conserved ABTS binding site close to the Cu T1 site.

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680 **TABLES**

681

682 **Table 1: Kinetics Parameters of Pp4816 and Pa5930 recombinant laccases for the**
 683 **substrates ABTS, 2,6-DMP, and ferrocyanide.**

Laccase	Substrate	K_m (mM)	k_{cat} (s⁻¹)	k_{cat}/K_m (mM⁻¹ s⁻¹)
Pp4816	ABTS	0.31 ± 0.03*	10.1 ± 2.5	32.6
	2,6-DMP	6.33 ± 1.32	0.03 ± 0.004	0.005
	Ferrocyanide	0.47 ± 0.24	255.0 ± 24	542.5
Pa5930	ABTS	0.33 ± 0.04*	2.31 ± 0.26	7.0
	2,6-DMP	3.11 ± 0.85	0.032 ± 0.003	0.01
	Ferrocyanide	1.02 ± 0.7	87.4 ± 21	85.7

684 ***Both enzymes showed sigmoidal kinetic with ABTS. For this substrate, the $K_{0.5}$**
 685 **(substrate concentration that generates a half-maximal velocity and is operationally**
 686 **similar to the Michaelis constant, K_m) was determined.**

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688 **Table 2:** Amine degradation by Pp4816 and Pa5930 laccases. ^a: With ABTS as mediator;

689 ^b: Without ABTS.

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% Degraded amine

Laccase	Tyramine	Histamine	Putrescine	Dopamine	Phenylethyl amine
Pa5930	70 ^a /0 ^b	0 ^{a,b}	0 ^{a,b}	97 ^a /55.2 ^b	0 ^{a,b}
Pp4816	93 ^a /0 ^b	0 ^{a,b}	0 ^{a,b}	100 ^a /96 ^b	0 ^{a,b}

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693 **Table 3:** Data collection and refinement statistics for *Pediococcus* laccases.

	Pa5930 pH	Pa5930 pH	Pp4816 pH	Pa5930 pH 3.0
	8.5	7.5	4.0	
Crystallization				
Crystallization	30%	10% PEG8000	83 mM	95 mM NaCitate
mixture	PEG1000	10% ethylene glycol	NaCitate	pH 3.0, 3.0%
	0.1 M Tris-HCl pH 8.5	glycol	pH 4.0,	PEG 8000, 7.8%
		0.1 M HEPES	670 mM	PEG 400, 1.2%
		pH 7.5	Li ₂ SO ₄ ,	DMSO, 114 mM
			8 mM each:	Benzamidine
			Gln, Asp,	HCL
			Gly, Pro	
Additions for crystal harvesting	PEG 3350 increased to 35%	PEG8000 and ethylene glycol increased to 20%	None	None
Data collection				
Wavelength (Å)	0.97925	0.97928	0.9202	0.9202
Space group	P2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁	P2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁	P3 ₂ 21	P2 ₁
Cell dimensions				
<i>a, b, c</i> (Å)	51.8, 94.3,	52.1, 78.2,	127.4, 127.4,	56.,1 147.3,
	97.6	162.5	75.3	65.5

α, β, γ ($^{\circ}$)	90, 90, 90	90, 90, 90	90, 90, 120	90, 98.6, 90
Resolution (\AA)	94.3-2.5 (2.5-2.6)	162.5-2.0 (2.05-2.0)	110-2.3 (2.4-2.3)	73.7-1.8(1.9-1.8)
No. reflections	12464 (14100)	304133 (21951)	29853 (2931)	96841 (9676)
R_{sym} or R_{merge}	0.14 (0.84)	0.08 (0.61)	0.34 (0.70)	0.19 (0.42)
R_{pim}	0.06 (0.35)	0.04 (0.29)	-	-
$I / \sigma I$	7.9 (2.2)	11.9 (2.7)	4.47 (1.76)	35.52 (0.71)
Completeness (%)	100 (100)	99.9 (99.8)	99.5 (98.3)	100 (100)
Redundancy	7.3 (7.5)	6.7 (6.3)	4.73	2.55
Refinement				
$R_{\text{work}} / R_{\text{free}}$	0.22/0.27	0.19/0.22	0.18/0.22	0.14/0.17
No. atoms				
Protein	3697	3792	4040	7674
Ligand/ion	4	4/4	5/2	21
Water	50	276	474	614
B -factors				
Protein	52.8	32.5	29.1	46.6
Ligand/ion	59.5	49.2/42.6	25.9	50.1
Water	41.3	38.8	28.4	53.0
R.m.s. deviations				
Bond lengths (\AA)	0.003	0.004	0.002	0.032

Bond angles	1.3	1.2	1.9	2.63
(°)				
Ramachandran				
(%)	92.37	93.62	95.85	94.92
Favoured	7.19	5.96	3.75	4.34
Allowed	0.44	0.43	0.40	0.74
Disallowed				
PDB code	6Z0J	6Z0K	6XJ0	6XIZ

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FIG 1: Multiple sequence alignment and conservation scoring of the *L. plantarum* J16, *Lactobacillus apis*-52100, *Lactococcus lactis*-9504, Pa5930, and Pp4816 laccases using Praline software (Bawono and Heringa 2014). The sequences of *L. apis* and *L. lactis* are representative of longest and shortest C-terminus groups in LAB, surrounded respectively in red and grey in Fig. S4. The scoring scheme works from 0 for the least conserved alignment position, up to 10 for the most conserved alignment position, the identical conserved residues are indicated by asterisks (color scale indicated on top). Dashes indicate gaps to maximize alignment. Encased inside boxes are the motifs that form the four copper ligands and are highly conserved in laccases (conserved sequence of these motifs are HXHG, HXH, HXXHXH, and HCHXXXHXXXM/L/F (Sharma, *et al.* 2007). C-terminal Met residues are highlighted in yellow, and His in purple.

173x371mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIG 2: Purification and biochemical characterization of Pp4816 laccase from *P. pentosaceus*. (A) Aliquots of the fractions from the different purification steps of the Pp4816 laccase were analyzed by PageBlue-stained 7.5% SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. Lane M1, Amersham™ ECL™ Rainbow™ Marker - Full range; lanes 1-8, consecutive fractions obtained after elution of the bound proteins from the Ni²⁺-NTA agarose matrix; lane 9, column washing fraction; lane 10, unbound proteins collected in the flow-through; lane 11, crude cell extract, corresponding to the loaded sample on the column; lane 12, whole-cell proteins from an induced culture; lane 13, whole-cell proteins from a non-induced culture; and lane M2, Pierce™ Prestained Protein MW Marker. (B) UV-Visible spectrum of purified recombinant Pp4816 laccase in 50 mM sodium phosphate, pH 6.5 buffer. Only the range 350-800 nm wavelength is shown. (C) pH effect on the activity of the Pp4816 enzyme toward ABTS (filled circle) and 2,6-DMP (filled square). Enzyme activity is plotted as a percentage relative to the maximum value (% relative activity). The values are means ± standard deviations from triplicate assays. (D) Temperature dependence and (E) T₅₀ of the Pp4816 laccase are determined against ABTS. In D, the maximum value was assumed as 100% activity and the others were calculated proportionally. In E, relative activities were calculated considering the OD₄₂₀ increase obtained at 28°C as 100% activity; the resulting percentages are plotted against the pretreatment temperature. The values are means ± standard deviations from triplicate assays.

274x159mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIG 3: Effect of different putative inhibitors on Pp4816 (green) and Pa5930 (orange) laccases. EDC: N-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl)-N'-ethyl carbodiimide; Phenan.: 1,10-phenanthroline; Cyclop.: cyclopropenyl; Depren.: deprenyl; Clorgyl.: clorgyline; Semicarb.: semicarbazide; Rasag.: rasagiline; Parg.: pargyline ; Bipy.: 2,2'-bipyridyl ; Thio. ac.: thioglycolic acid; Na Az.: sodium azide; ZnCl₂: zinc chloride; Cys.: cysteine HCl monohydrate; EDTA: ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; NaCl: sodium chloride; NaF: sodium fluoride; Control means an enzyme assay in absence of inhibitors. The remaining activity with the different potential inhibitors is graphed as percentage respect to the control (assumed as 100% of enzyme activity). Values are means \pm standard deviations of triplicate assays.

214x189mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIG 4: Structure of *Pediococcus* laccases Pa5930 and Pp4816. (A) Structural superposition of both *Pediococcus* laccases with each cupredoxin-like domain color-coded (1 in cyan, 2 in yellow, and 3 in magenta). The long coil region connecting domain 2 with 3 is colored in red and the C-terminal extension of Pp4816 is colored in pale orange. The four copper ions are shown as yellow spheres. (B) Surface representation of domains 2 and cartoon representation of domain 1, all domains are color-coded. (C) Superposition of each cupredoxin domain at *Pediococcus* laccases Pa5930 (in blue) and Pp4816 (in pale orange) together with CotA of *B. subtilis* (in magenta, PDB: 3ZDW) and CueO of *E. coli* (in green, PDB: 4E9T). (D) C-terminal sequence alignment of *Pediococcus* laccases highlighting the presence of Met (in yellow) and His (in purple) residues.

338x190mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIG 5. Copper coordination and TNC channel. (A) View of the T1 Cu and TNC site of coordination for superposed Pa5930 and Pp4816 laccases. Cu ions (in yellow) and water molecules at the TNC (W, in red) are rendered as spheres. The coordinating residues are color-coded (blue for Pa5930 and pale orange for Pp4816). The cartoon represents domain 1 (in cyan) and domain 3 (in magenta), which scaffold the copper-binding motifs. The electron density map around the Cu ions is contoured at 1 σ . (B) Detail of C-terminal extension of Pp4816 (orange) that caps and inserts several residues into the TNC channel (C) Pa5930 (blue) lacks this C-terminal extension and has a more exposed TNC. (D) Ascomycete laccases' C-terminal plugs (PDB 1GW0, rendered gray), penetrate the TNC channel in a similar location as Pp4816's C-terminus. Waters observed in the Pa5930 and Pp4816 crystal structures leading to the TNC are modelled as red spheres.

338x190mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIG 6: Analysis of the substrate binding site in CotA with the Pa5930 and Pp4816 laccases (A) Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue) with CotA (in yellow) showing the two binding sites for ABTS (represented in atoms and transparent surface in orange). The long coil region connecting domain 2 with 3 is colored in red in both structures. (B) Closeup of ABTS binding at the T1 Cu site, the conserved laccase active site. Pa5930 shows clashes with ABTS bound to CotA. (C) Closeup of ABTS binding at an alternative site in CotA, located at the long coil region (in red) which also shows clashes with Pa5930. (D) Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue) and Pp4816 (in pale orange) laccases showing Met residues that lie at the conserved ABTS binding site close to the Cu T1 site.

338x190mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Table S1. Root mean square deviations (r.m.s.d.), in Å, for the superposition of laccase structures.

	CueO (PDB: 4E9T)	CotA (PDB: 3ZDW)	Pa5930	Pp4816
Rmsd CueO (Å)	-	1.56 (412)	1.28 (401)	1.30 (398)
Rmsd CotA (Å)		-	1.33 (404)	1.47 (411)
Rmsd Pa5930 (Å)			-	0.85 (464)
Rmsd Pp4816 (Å)				-

The number of C α atoms superimposed is indicated between parentheses.

Table S2. Substrates used at pH 3.0 for soaking or co-crystallization with laccase Pa5930.

Substrates
ABTS
Acetovanillone
Bromophenol blue
Caffeic acid
Chlorophenol red
p-Coumaric acid
Cresol red
2,6-Dimethoxyphenol
3,4-Dimethoxyphenol
3,4-(Dimethoxyphenyl)methanol
Ferulic acid
Guaiacol
Hydroquinone
Lactic acid
Phenol Red
Syringaldehyde
L-Tyrosine

FIG. S1. Kinetic analysis of recombinant laccases Pp4816 and Pa5930. Pp4816 (A, B, and C) and Pa5930 (D, E, and F) laccases were tested with the substrates ABTS (A, D), ferrocyanide (B, E), and 2,6-DMP (C, F). Oxidation of ABTS and ferrocyanide was followed by registering the OD at 420, and that of 2,6-DMP at 468. Reaction rates were obtained from the linear portion of the progress graph and are plotted against the corresponding substrate concentrations. The kinetic data have been fitted by nonlinear regression to an empirical sigmoid equation, the Hill equation (ABTS, graphs A and D) and to a hyperbolic equation (ferrocyanide and 2,6-DMP, that is B, C, E and F) with the Prism GraphPad program. Kinetic experiments were repeated at least three times with various enzyme concentrations. Only a representative kinetic experiment for each laccase and each substrate, together with resulting fitted substrate-rate curve, is depicted.

272x175mm (300 x 300 DPI)

25 FIG. S2. Pa5930 structure at pH 7.5 and 8.5. Superposition of domain 3 in the structures of Pa5930 at Tris-
26 HCl pH 8.5 and HEPES pH 7.5 (in blue hues). The C terminal end of Pa5930 at Tris-HCl pH 8.5 was traced till
27 residue 461 while at HEPES pH 7.5 was traced till residue 471. Structures of domain 3 at Pa5930 (in blue
28 hues) and Pp4816 (in orange) are superposed.

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25 FIG. S3. Structural comparison of Pa5930 and Pp4816 laccases with CotA and CueO. Pa5930 and Pp4816
26 structures are superposed, and CotA and CueO are shown as individual structures. The three cupredoxin-like
27 domains are color-coded and the long coil region between domain 2 and 3 is colored in red. The Cu ions are
28 also shown in yellow.

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FIG. S4. Molecular Phylogenetic analysis by Maximum Likelihood method of LAB laccases from <https://lccd.biocatnet.de/>. Sequences in the grey zone contain the shorter C terminus, intermediate length in the blue, longer in the green, and longest in the red zone. The evolutionary history was inferred in MEGA7 (S. Kumar, G. Stecher, and K. Tamura, Mol Biol Evol 33:1870-1874, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msw054>) by the Maximum Likelihood method based on the JTT matrix-based model (D.T. Jones, W.R. Taylor, and J.M. Thornton, Comput Appl Biosci 8:275-282, 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/8.3.275>). Initial trees were obtained by Neighbor-Join and BioNJ algorithms to a matrix of pairwise distances using a JTT model. Branch lengths indicate the number of substitutions per site. The analysis involved 156 sequences and 259 positions, eliminating all gaps and missing data.

190x275mm (300 x 300 DPI)

25 FIG. S5. Analysis of the Met rich regions. A) Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue), Pp4816 (in orange) and
 26 CueO (PDB 4E9T, in green) highlighting the C-terminal end of the *Pediococcus* laccases and Met-rich insert
 27 at CueO. A sequence alignment between these laccases, including CotA, shows the extension of C-terminal
 28 domain of Pa5930 and Pp4816 and the presence of Met residues (in yellow) and His (in purple). B) In
 29 Pp4816, five Met (designated as an asterisk) at the C-terminal end form a hydrophobic patch at the protein
 30 surface.

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FIG. S6. Copper coordination site. A) Superposed Pa5930 (in blue), Pp4816 (in orange), CueO (PDB 4E9T, in green) and CotA (PDB: 3ZDW, in magenta) showing Cu ions (in yellow) and the residues involved in their coordination at CuT1 and TNC site. The cupredoxin-like domains where Cu coordination lies are shown as surface in transparency and color-coded. B) Superposed Pa5930 and Pp4816 structures showing the Cu ions and residues involved in their coordination at the TNC site together with the acidic residues that surround the TNC site at each laccase.

338x190mm (300 x 300 DPI)

25 FIG. S7. The TNC channel. Superposition of Pa5930 (in blue) and Pp4816 (in orange) crystal structures.
26 Waters (modelled as red spheres) leading to the TNC were observed in the Pp4816. The C-terminal
27 extension of Pp4816, distal from the TNC, caps the channel and inserts several residues into it. Meanwhile
28 Pa5930 lacks this C-terminal extension and has a more exposed TNC.

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FIG. S8. Comparison of Pa5930 at pH=3.5 and pH=7.5. A) Structural overview of the Pa5930 pH 3.5 structure. Two molecules (green and dark green) were observed in the asymmetric unit. B) A benzamidine coordinates the packing of the two copies of Pa5930 by stacking in between Tyr12 of each. Polar bonds between each molecules Asp30 and benzamidine also stabilize the interface. C) Comparison of the Pa5930 pH 3.5 (green) and Pa5930 pH 7.5 (blue) structure reveal nearly perfect structural alignment.

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FIG. S9. Met residues at the conserved substrate binding site. Superposed structures of Pa5930 (in blue), Pp4816 (in pale orange) and CueO (in green, PDB: 4E9T) showing the ABTS binding site as surface in transparency from CotA structure (PDB: 3ZDW). The Met-rich region of CueO lie at the ABTS binding site as well as M347 in Pa5930 or M389 in Pp4816 precluding substrate binding.

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